

DETERMINANTS OF INTRA-INDUSTRY TRADE BETWEEN GEORGIA AND SELECTED EUROPEAN COUNTRIES AND TURKEY

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ABSTRACT

When Georgia's foreign trade structure is examined, it is seen that it is an important trade partner of Turkey and the European Union. Although Georgia wants to increase its foreign trade with liberalization policies, it has a foreign trade deficit because of production diversity and insufficient volume. As the financing of the foreign trade deficit with foreign capital and debt is not sustainable in the long term, measuring the level of intra-industry trade and the factors that determine trade of Georgia with its trade partners become important. In this context, the main purpose of the study is to measure Georgia's intra-industry trade with selected European countries and Turkey and to determine its determinants. The study period covers for the year 2008-2022. The Grubel-Lloyd index, that is frequently preferred in the literature, was used to measure Georgia's intra-industry trade with its trade partners, and the system generalized moments (GMM) method, that is a panel data estimation method, was used to estimate the determinants of intra-industry trade. When Georgia's average intra-industry trade index for the year 2008-2022 is examined; it is revealed that it has more intensive intra-industry trade with Germany, Italy, England, Netherlands, Greece and Turkey than other selected EU member countries. In addition, Georgia has very low intra-industry trade with Sweden, Austria, Czech Republic, Romania and Bulgaria. Furthermore, the system GMM estimation results show that the market size (GDP), per capita GDP indicating the level of development and foreign trade deficit between trading partners positively affects intra-industry trade, while the market size difference between countries, per capita GDP difference, trade imbalance and physical distance increase reduce intra-industry trade.

Keywords: Georgia, European Union, Türkiye, Intra-industry trade, GMM.

Introduction

Classical international trade theory suggests that countries should focus on producing goods in which they have a comparative advantage. However, with the deep integration of nations into the global economy after World War II, foreign trade between countries has become more complex and cannot be explained by classical trade theories. The increasing trade of industrial products, especially among developed countries, has not met the expectations that countries will specialize in certain sectors depending on their density. The increase in trade between countries with the same or similar factor endowments could not be explained by classical foreign trade theories, and intra-industry trade theory was put forward. Intra-industry trade refers to the exchange of similar products belonging to the same industry. In other words, intra-industry trade is a form of foreign trade based on the simultaneous import and export of products that fall into the same industry class but have some differences in terms of quality, appearance, brand and usage characteristics.

There are numerous studies on intra-industry trade in existing literature. These studies can be generally divided into two groups where the first group focuses on

explaining the reasons for the existence of intra-industry trade while the second group focuses on measuring the extent of intra-industry trade. Although the concept of intra-industry trade was used only to explain trade between countries when it first emerged, it began to consider not only whether intra-industry trade exists or the degree of intra-industry trade, but also the factors affecting this trade in later periods. Although there are numerous empirical studies in the literature that contribute to the determinants of intra-industry trade, most of them have focused only on developed countries where trade flows are equivalent due to similar demand structures and production technologies. For this reason, studies on the determinants of intra-industry trade in developing countries have been insufficient. The production of goods and mutual trade in developing or underdeveloped countries are less compared to developed countries; however, this does not mean that intra-industry trade does not exist among underdeveloped countries.

After gaining independence in 1991, Georgia experienced political turmoil and economic fluctuations until 2008. The delays in transitioning to a liberal economy are one of the main features of this period. However, Georgia's strategic location has strengthened

Russia's control over the country, while at the same time strengthened the West's desire to get closer to Georgia, that led to increased cooperation. Following the end of the war in Georgia in 2008, the country's dependence on Russia for foreign trade has decreased, and the increase in trade with the European Union and Türkiye has been one of the main reasons for this change.

Georgia, strategically located at the center of transit trade to Europe, has attracted the attention not only to the West but also to China within the scope of the New Silk Road Project. Georgia, which is trying to gain a more active place in world trade, evaluates the transit passage of products and energy transmission lines from China as an opportunity to overcome the current account deficit problem caused by external dependency, especially in sectors such as oil and technology. Georgia anticipates that the income to be obtained from transit trade will partially cover its foreign trade deficit and therefore aims to eliminate its external deficit in the long term by developing its intra-industry trade with Europe and Türkiye. Furthermore, considering that financing the external deficit through foreign capital and partial borrowing is not sustainable, Georgia has put into many practices that encourage direct foreign capital investments. However, the fact that the foreign direct investments in the country are largely directed to non-productive areas such as construction and gambling tourism that clearly demonstrates the importance of intra-industry trade that Georgia carries out with its trade partners.

In this context, the main purpose of the study is to measure the level of intra-industry trade between Georgia, which is in the category of transition economies, and selected European countries and Türkiye, and to analyze the determinants of this trade. In this context, the intra-industry trade levels of STIC Rev4 Level 1 (1 Digit) sub-sectors were measured using the Grubel and Lloyd index. In addition, the Grubel-Lloyd index and 10 different estimation models were used to reveal the determinants of trade. First, the theoretical approaches and literature of intra-industry trade were examined. Then, the factors determining intra-industry trade and relevant academic studies in this field were discussed. In the last section, that includes econometric analyses, applications made to reveal the determinants of intra-industry trade between Georgia, selected European countries and Turkey were included.

1. Intra-Industry Trade: Theory and Literature

Intra-industry trade is a concept that has gained importance with the liberalization of world trade. With the end of World War II, countries living in close geographies and having economic relations around the world have initiated economic unification movements among themselves. In addition, during this period, multi-faceted negotiations were held within the framework of GATT for the liberalization of international trade, reduction of customs duties, removal of bureaucratic barriers in world trade and paving the way for bilateral trade. Due to all these developments, intra-industry trade, which is defined as simultaneous and reciprocal trade of similar goods in the same product category, has constituted a significant part of world trade.

Intra-industry trade refers to the exchange of similar products belonging to the same industry. The concept of intra-industry trade is generally used in international trade where the same type of goods or services are both imported and exported. In this type of trade, all goods from 0 to 9 that fall into the SITC goods classification are included in the trade.

According to Nigel Grimwade (1989), an explanation for intra-industry trade cannot be found within the framework of Classical and Neo-classical trade theories. These theories only predict inter-industry specialization and trade. Traditional foreign trade theories are based on David Ricardo's and Heckscher-Ohlin theories that attempt to explain the formation of international trade. Both offer the idea of comparative advantage and an explanation of why countries trade. However, many economists state that countries with the same factor endowments will not trade domestically and will not produce goods, which suggests that these models provide no explanation for intra-industry trade. For this reason, some economists have developed new explanations for intra-industry trade. According to a view put forward by J.M. Finger in 1975, intra-industry trade was considered "unimportant" because existing classifications placed goods with heterogeneous factor endowments in a single industry. However, it is observed that intra-industry trade continues even when industries are separated in detail. Therefore, this evidence should be ignored (Finger, 1975).

In general, the most comprehensive and widely accepted explanation in the literature is Paul Krugman's New Trade Theory. According to Krugman, economies specialize in benefiting from increasing returns rather than following differences in their regional equipment (as claimed by the Neoclassical theory). Trade allows countries to specialize in a limited variety of production and thus to benefit from increasing returns (i.e. economies of scale) but without reducing the variety of goods available for consumption (Krugman, 1981).

There are also those who defend the opposite view to that advocated by J.M. Finger (1975) and Paul Krugman (1981). One of those who defend the opposite view is the American economist Donald R. Davis. Donald R. Davis argued that both the Heckscher-Ohlin and Ricardo models are still valid in explaining intra-industry trade. According to Donald R. Davis, the models developed by Heckscher-Ohlin and Ricardo show that intra-industry trade can still occur in the traditional environment even with constant returns to scale. In addition, the Heckscher-Ohlin and Ricardo models argue that countries with the same factor endowments can still trade due to differences in technology (Davis, 1995).

As can be seen, there have been multiple views and definitions regarding intra-industry trade depending on different periods. In addition, technological developments that emerged with the liberalization of world trade, mass production and product diversity increased, and thus, international trade was divided into two different types: intra-industry and inter-industry trade. On the other hand, intra-industry trade has been divided into multiple and complementary subgroups regarding the nature and characteristics of the product.

In the existing literature, there are multiple different calculation methods for measuring the level of intra-industry trade. These methods are classified into two separate groups as static and dynamic measurement methods and were put forward by different researchers in different periods (Llyod and Lee, 2002; Yuan, 2012).

Static measurement methods generally assess the level of intra-industry trade using data from a specific period. These methods measure the intensity of trade between products at a specific time period but usually provide a single snapshot and do not take into account changes over time. For example, the methods proposed by Grubel and Lloyd (1975), Greenaway and Milner (1983), Brühlhart (1994), Menon & Dixon (1997) and Azhar & Elliott (2008) are static measurement methods.

Dynamic measurement methods, unlike static measurement methods, evaluate the evolution of intra-industry trade over time. These methods try to understand the dynamics of intra-industry trade by following trade flows in a certain period. Shelburne (1993) marginal intra-industry trade index (MIIT) is a dynamic measurement method. In addition, the indices put forward by Verdoorn (1960), Michaely (1962), Kojima (1964), Balassa (1966), Aquino (1978), Loertscher & Wolter (1980), Glejser et al. (1982), Hamilton and Kniest (1991), Greenaway et al. (1994), Thom and McDowell (1999) are also dynamic measurement methods and all of these indices are designed to capture changes over time (Andresen, 2010).

In this study, the Grubel-Lloyd index, which is the most frequently used index by researchers in measuring Georgia's intra-industry trade between European countries and Turkey, was used. The index, developed by Herb Grubel and Peter Lloyd, is generally formulated as follows:

$$IIT_i = 1 - \frac{|X_i - M_i|}{(X_i + M_i)} * 100$$

In this equation, IIT_i is the intra-industry trade coefficient, X_i is the exporter of product i , M_i is the importer of product i , $(X_i + M_i)$ is the foreign trade volume of product i , $|X_i - M_i|$ is the foreign trade balance of product i . The intra-industry trade value measured by this equation is valued between 0 and 1. As the value approaches 0, the intra-industry trade level decreases, while as it approaches 1, the intra-industry trade level increases. When the value of exports fully covers the value of imports, the index value is equal to 100, and when exports are made and imports are not made, or vice versa, the index value is assumed to be zero (Grubel and Lloyd, 1975).

1.1. Determinants of Intra-Industry Trade

Intra-industry trade is shaped by the influence of economic, political and socio-cultural factors between countries. Country-specific determinants include elements such as a country's economic situation, per capita income level, development level, factor endowment, and level of economic and political integration. These factors significantly determine the direction and volume of trade between countries. Industry-specific factors depend on the structural characteristics of a partic-

ular sector; human capital intensity, technological development, economies of scale and degree of product differentiation are prominent elements in this context (Hartman-Henderson and Sheldon, 1993; Bano, 2013).

Political and institutional determinants also have a significant impact on trade. Regulations such as trade agreements, tariffs, export and import incentives can directly affect the direction of trade (Loertscher and Wolter, 1980). In addition, geographical proximity, transportation costs, and common cultural ties are among the factors that facilitate trade. Border trade is generally more intense between countries with similar cultures, histories, and languages (Falvey, 1981; Sharma, 1999).

The concept of intra-industry trade, when it first emerged, was used only to explain trade between countries. However, in the 1980s, studies not only on whether there was intra-industry trade or measuring the degree of intra-industry trade but also studies that considered the factors that could affect this trade started to increase. Especially in this period, studies by authors such as Dixit and Stiglitz (1977), followed by Balassa (1979), Lancaster (1979), Tharakan (1984), Havrylyshyn & Civan (1985), Flam & Helpman (1987), Manrique (1987), Ballance et al. (1992) have made significant contributions to the literature. Studies investigating the factors determining intra-industry trade have gained momentum since the 2000s. Bhattacharyya (2002), Thorpe & Zhang (2005), Stanley & Clark (2006), Sunde et al. (2009), Zhang & Clark (2009), Sawyer et al. (2010), Mulenga (2012), Yuan (2012), Sotomayor (2012), Saray (2013), Lapinska (2014), Trupkiewicz (2015), Nisa (2017), Justyna et al. (2019), Vidya & Prabheesh (2019), Nguyen et al. (2020), Ozer (2021), Gonzalez et al. (2022), Ekayanti et al. (2023) and Aggarwal (2023) have comprehensively examined the factors affecting intra-industry trade in different periods and different regions. These studies have made valuable contributions to literature with theoretical and empirical approaches, allowing us to better understand the dynamics of intra-industry trade.

When the intra-industry trade dynamics of Georgia with its selected trading partners are examined, it is seen that economic factors such as market sizes and income differences, as well as factors such as geographical distance and foreign trade balance are decisive. While economic size and level of development play a role in increasing trade, factors such as physical distance and trade imbalances can have negative effects. In this context, both economic and socio-cultural factors are among the basic elements shaping Georgia's trade relations.

2. Models and Variables Used in Georgia's Intra-Industry Trade Analysis

The model generally used in intra-industry trade analysis is as follows:

$$IIT_i = f(X_{ik})$$

In the equation, IIT_i represents the intra-industry trade rates measured for country i . X_{ik} The equation represents the explanatory variables expected to have an effect on intra-industry trade. Table 1 below shows the explanatory variables used in the model and the theoretically expected coefficient signs.

Table 1

Determinants of Intra-Industry Trade	
Explanatory Variables	Expected Signs
Market Sizes of Countries (GDP \$)	+
Market Size Differences of Countries (GDPD\$)	-
Development Level of Countries (GDPPRC \$)	+/-
Development Level Differences Between Countries (GDPPRC D \$)	-
Physical Distance Between Countries (DIS, Kilometers)	-
Border Trade and Same Sea Sharing (BTR)	+
Openness Level of the National Economy to the Outside World (EO%)	+
Foreign Trade Imbalance (FTI \$)	-

Source: Table created by the author.

The analysis of the determinants of Georgia's intra-industry trade with selected European countries and Türkiye was carried out individually for each group of goods coded from 0 to 9 according to STIC Rev4 Level 1 (1 Digit). The period of the analysis was determined as 2008 to 2022. The reason for choosing the data period as 2008 to 2022 is that there is no restriction in accessing the data of all selected countries at the same time and that Georgia's mutual trade with Europe and Türkiye intensified due to the war between Georgia and Russia in 2008. The countries included in the analysis are Austria, Germany, Belgium, Bulgaria, United Kingdom, Czech Republic, France, Netherlands, Switzerland, Italy, Spain, Poland, Romania, Greece, Ukraine, Sweden, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova and Türkiye, respectively. The intra-industry trade volumes of the countries used in the analysis and the independent variables of the established models were calculated with the Grubel and Lloyd index. In addition, data for all variables used in the analysis were obtained from the World Bank, International Monetary Fund, Turkish Statistical Institute and Georgian Statistical Institute. All monetary data used are in US Dollars.

3. Econometric Method: Dynamic Panel Data Generalized Method of Moments (GMM)

When the studies that make estimations with the standard panel data method are examined, it is seen that the time dimension is generally smaller than the number of observations. In these estimations, when the T-time dimension is smaller than the N-observation number, the least squares estimation method gives inconsistent results. When the T-time dimension is smaller than the N-observation number, the dynamic panel data (GMM) estimation method gives more accurate results (Hayakawa, 2005). For this reason, the dynamic panel data estimation method (GMM) was preferred in the study to reveal the determinants of Georgia's intra-industry trade with selected European countries and Türkiye.

The basic ideas of GMM are based on the studies of Anderson & Hsiao (1981, 1982), Hansen (1982), Arellano & Bond (1991), Blundell & Bond (1998). In dynamic panel data analysis, the generalized method of moments is divided into two as first difference-GMM and system-GMM under different assumptions. The first model including dynamic panel data is the first difference model. In other words, in the first stage, the first difference is taken to eliminate the observed heterogeneity, then the difference-GMM method is applied by

including the previous period value of the dependent variable as an instrumental variable in the model (Arellano & Bond, 1991). In existing literature, this method is known as the first difference method or the Arellano-Bond estimator. Arellano-Bover (1995) and Blundell-Bond (1998) constructed the system-GMM model by considering that the first differences of the instrumental variables are uncorrelated with the fixed effects. By combining the difference and level equations in the system-GMM model, more instrumental variables can be included in the model, thus the estimates of the system-GMM approach are stronger and more reliable than the difference-GMM approach (Arellano and Bover, 1995). For this reason, the system-GMM estimation method is used extensively in econometric analyses.

The system-GMM estimator is based on the moment conditions given in the equation below (Blundell and Bond, 1998).

$$\gamma_s = \frac{\beta'_{-1} Z_1 W_N^{-1} Z_1' \beta}{\beta'_{-1} Z_1 W_N^{-1} Z_1' \beta_{-1}} ; \beta_i = (\Delta y_i' y_i)'$$

The validity of the System-GMM estimation results is checked with two different tests (Sargan-Hansen and Autocorrelation). The Sargan-Hansen test provides information about whether the instrumental variables fully reflect the main variables, their endogeneity and suitability. The second test checks the first- and second-degree autocorrelation status in the error terms (Hansen, 2007).

Within the framework of the explanations above, the estimation models to be used in this study are given in Tables 2 and 3 below. The data related to the dependent variable, intra-industry trade variable, in the estimation models in question are the previously calculated Grubel-Lloyd index values. Again, the explanatory variables given in the tables below are presented in Table 1. When Table 1, which shows the IIT levels given in the second part of the study, is carefully examined, it is seen that Georgia has intensive intra-industry trade with selected European countries and Turkey in the product groups with STIC codes 0, 1, 2, 5 and 6, while intra-industry trade is weak in the product groups with codes 3, 4, 7, 8 and 9. Therefore, the determinants of intra-industry trade are estimated separately and one by one for the product groups with intensive and weak trade. The estimated econometric equations are given in Tables 2 and 3 below.

List of Estimation Models for Goods Groups Where IIT is Strong

Model 1 (STIC 0)	$IIT_{FALA} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IIT_{FALA,t-1} + \beta_2 GDP_{FALA,t} + \beta_3 GDPPRC_{FALA,t} + \beta_4 GDPD_{FALA,t} + \beta_5 GDPPRCD_{FALA,t} + \beta_6 EO_{FALA,t} + \beta_7 FTI_{FALA,t} + \beta_8 DIS_{FALA,t} + \varepsilon_{FALA,t}$
Model 2 (STIC 1)	$IIT_{BAT} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IIT_{BAT,t-1} + \beta_2 GDP_{BAT,t} + \beta_3 GDPPRC_{BAT,t} + \beta_4 GDPD_{BAT,t} + \beta_5 GDPPRCD_{BAT,t} + \beta_6 EO_{BAT,t} + \beta_7 FTI_{BAT,t} + \beta_8 DIS_{BAT,t} + \varepsilon_{BAT,t}$
Model 3 (STIC 2)	$IIT_{CMIEF} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IIT_{CMIEF,t-1} + \beta_2 GDP_{CMIEF,t} + \beta_3 GDPPRC_{CMIEF,t} + \beta_4 GDPD_{CMIEF,t} + \beta_5 GDPPRCD_{CMIEF,t} + \beta_6 EO_{CMIEF,t} + \beta_7 FTI_{CMIEF,t} + \beta_8 DIS_{CMIEF,t} + \varepsilon_{CMIEF,t}$
Model 4 (STIC 5)	$IIT_{CARP} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IIT_{CARP,t-1} + \beta_2 GDP_{CARP,t} + \beta_3 GDPPRC_{CARP,t} + \beta_4 GDPD_{CARP,t} + \beta_5 GDPPRCD_{CARP,t} + \beta_6 EO_{CARP,t} + \beta_7 FTI_{CARP,t} + \beta_8 DIS_{CARP,t} + \varepsilon_{CARP,t}$
Model 6 (STIC 6)	$IIT_{MGCCM} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IIT_{MGCCM,t-1} + \beta_2 GDP_{MGCCM,t} + \beta_3 GDPPRC_{MGCCM,t} + \beta_4 GDPD_{MGCCM,t} + \beta_5 GDPPRCD_{MGCCM,t} + \beta_6 EO_{MGCCM,t} + \beta_7 FTI_{MGCCM,t} + \beta_8 DIS_{MGCCM,t} + \varepsilon_{MGCCM,t}$

NOTE: *i* in the equations represents the *i*th country in that commodity group, and *t* represents the period 2008-2022. All variables in the models are in logarithmic form.

In Table 2, the 1st Model is the econometric equation created to estimate the determinants of IIT among the countries under study in the STIC 0 coded live animals and foodstuffs (FALA) goods group. Similarly, the 2nd Model is the STIC 1 coded beverage and tobacco products (BAT), the 3rd Model is the STIC 2

coded raw materials excluding fuel (CMIEF), the 4th Model is the STIC 5 coded chemical industry products not specified elsewhere (CARP) and the 5th Model is the STIC 6 coded processed goods divided into main classes (MGCCM) group.

Table 3

List of Estimation Models for Goods Groups Where IIT Is Weak

6. Model (STIC 3)	$IIT_{MYYAU} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IIT_{MFLRM,t-1} + \beta_2 GDP_{MFLRM,t} + \beta_3 GDPPRC_{MFLRM,t} + \beta_4 GDPD_{MFLRM,t} + \beta_5 GDPPRCD_{MFLRM,t} + \beta_6 EO_{MFLRM,t} + \beta_7 FTI_{MFLRM,t} + \beta_8 DIS_{MFLRM,t} + \varepsilon_{MFLRM,t}$
7. Model (STIC 4)	$IIT_{AVOFW} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IIT_{AVOFW,t-1} + \beta_2 GDP_{AVOFW,t} + \beta_3 GDPPRC_{AVOFW,t} + \beta_4 GDPD_{AVOFW,t} + \beta_5 GDPPRCD_{AVOFW,t} + \beta_6 EO_{AVOFW,t} + \beta_7 FTI_{AVOFW,t} + \beta_8 DIS_{AVOFW,t} + \varepsilon_{AVOFW,t}$
8. Model (STIC 7)	$IIT_{MTE} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IIT_{MTE,t-1} + \beta_2 GDP_{MTE,t} + \beta_3 GDPPRC_{MTE,t} + \beta_4 GDPD_{MTE,t} + \beta_5 GDPPRCD_{MTE,t} + \beta_6 EO_{MTE,t} + \beta_7 FTI_{MTE,t} + \beta_8 DIS_{MTE,t} + \varepsilon_{MTE,t}$
9. Model (STIC 8)	$IIT_{MMA} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IIT_{MMA,t-1} + \beta_2 GDP_{MMA,t} + \beta_3 GDPPRC_{MMA,t} + \beta_4 GDPD_{MMA,t} + \beta_5 GDPPRCD_{MMA,t} + \beta_6 EO_{MMA,t} + \beta_7 FTI_{MMA,t} + \beta_8 DIS_{MMA,t} + \varepsilon_{MMA,t}$
10. Model (STIC 9)	$IIT_{CTNCE} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IIT_{CTNCE,t-1} + \beta_2 GDP_{CTNCE,t} + \beta_3 GDPPRC_{CTNCE,t} + \beta_4 GDPD_{CTNCE,t} + \beta_5 GDPPRCD_{CTNCE,t} + \beta_6 EO_{CTNCE,t} + \beta_7 FTI_{CTNCE,t} + \beta_8 DIS_{CTNCE,t} + \varepsilon_{CTNCE,t}$

NOTE: In the equations, *i* represents the *i*. country in that commodity group, and *t* represents the period 2008-2022. All variables in the models are in logarithmic form.

In Table 3, Model 6 is the econometric equation created to estimate the determinants of IIT among the countries under study in the STIC 3 coded mineral fuels, oils and related products (MFLRM) commodity group. Similarly, Model 7 is the STIC 4 coded animal, vegetable fats and liquid oils (AVOFW), Model 8 is the STIC 7 coded machinery and vehicles (MTE), Model 9 is the STIC 8 coded miscellaneous manufactured goods (MMA) and Model 10 is the STIC 9 coded unclassified goods (CTNCE) group.

3.1. GMM Analysis Results

The results of the two-stage GMM analysis, which will reveal the determinants of Georgia's intra-industry trade with 19 selected European countries and Türkiye, are presented in Tables 4 and 5 below. The first table shows the estimation results for the commodity groups where Georgia's intra-industry trade with the selected countries is intense, and the second table shows the estimation results for the commodity groups where Georgia's intra-industry trade with the selected countries is weak.

Table 4

SGMM Estimation Results in Goods Groups with Strong Intra-Industry Trade

Variables / Models	IIT _{FALA}	IIT _{BAT}	IIT _{CMIEF}	IIT _{CARP}	IIT _{MGCCM}
SGMM _{FALA}	0.4649676***	-	-	-	-
SGMM _{BAT}	-	0.30001397*	-	-	-
SGMM _{CMIEF}	-	-	0.486227***	-	-
SGMM _{CARP}	-	-	-	0.134541***	-
SGMM _{MGCCM}	-	-	-	-	0.5474846***
GDP	0.1010087*	0.1797271***	0.0978106**	0.000769**	0.0816287*
GDP _{PRC}	-0.1422677**	-0.132751	-0.042353	-0.1282528*	0.0361753
GDP _D	-0.0089912**	-0.0057106	-0.0064632***	-0.0022311	-0.0028104
GDP _{PRCD}	0.0061874	-0.0011726	-0.0075214***	-0.0007967	-0.0042914***
EO	-0.821008	0.1982964*	0.0073531	-0.81716	0.1311932***
FTI	-0.2250801	0.3858897	-0.002181	-0.2098346	0.2945231*
DIS	0.707524	0.0936284	-0.3390965***	-0.2442514**	0.0987748*
Number of Observations	300	300	300	300	300
Number of Countries	20	20	20	20	20
AR (1)	-3.49***	-2.41***	-2.97***	-2.23**	-3.00***
AR (2)	0.26**	0.79*	0.03***	0.62**	-1.12*
Sargan	13.72***	4.94**	5.28**	11.82**	17.21***

Note: *_ (0.10) 10% significant, **_ (0.5) 5% significant, ***_ (0.01) 1% significant.

Table 5

SGMM Estimation Results for Goods Groups with Weak Intra-Industry Trade

Variable / Model	IIT _{MELRM}	IIT _{AVOFW}	IIT _{MTE}	IIT _{MMA}	IIT _{CTNCE}
SGMM _{MELRM}	0.3927172***	-	-	-	-
SGMM _{AVOFW}	-	0.3242382*	-	-	-
SGMM _{MTE}	-	-	0.6065375***	-	-
SGMM _{MMA}	-	-	-	0.5199604***	-
SGMM _{CTNCE}	-	-	-	-	0.0711615***
GDP	0.069557	0.0577147	0.0153901	0.061306**	0.1156984**
GDP _{PRC}	0.0508412	0.0846235	-0.0847165***	0.049436	0.0932772
GDP _D	-0.0031868	-0.0019007	0.0004806	-0.0040701**	-0.0054795**
GDP _{PRCD}	-0.0012791	-0.0028337	0.0020149	-0.0010589	-0.0026552
EO	-0.0219399	0.00183	0.153571***	0.099748	0.0891602
FTI	0.1453947	0.1693716	0.2126612	-0.0276455	0.2260115
DIS	-0.1649955**	-0.1176474	0.015272	-0.1669674***	-0.2692776**
Number of Observations	300	300	300	300	300
Number of Countries	20	20	20	20	20
AR (1)	-2.22**	-1.75*	-2.98***	-2.70***	-2.96***
AR (2)	0.29*	-0.64	-1.68*	-0.55	0.53
Sargan	8.18	5.64	25.76***	4.05	7.29***

Note: *_ (0.10) 10% significant, **_ (0.5) 5% significant, ***_ (0.01) 1% significant.

The most important determinant of Georgia's intra-industry trade with the countries under study in general in all STIC level (1) product groups, as expected theoretically, has been found to be gross domestic product. The high production potential of countries creates higher national income and increases product diversity and demand for these goods. Therefore, as national income increases, product demand from Georgia's trade partners will increase in all product groups, and the same result will be valid for product demands from European countries and Turkey from Georgia, and the mutual intra-industry trade volume will increase. It should be noted that Georgia needs to increase product diversity for mutual strong intra-industry trade with its trade partners. Although the country provides production incentives, control and additional incentive policies need to be implemented for these incentives to be directed

from the tourism and construction sectors to the industrial sector and the R&D investments that feed it. In addition, the sale of agricultural and livestock sector products and minerals sold as raw materials as processed products will provide higher value-added income to the country. Again, for this transformation, industrial investments need to be revitalized in the country.

The second important factor determining Georgia's intra-industry trade with its trade partners in all product groups is the distance between countries. Theoretically, as the distance between countries increases, transportation costs increase, and thus intra-industry trade is negatively affected by this situation. As expected theoretically in this study, as the distance between countries increases, Georgia's intra-industry trade with Europe and Türkiye decreases. Georgia is a country dependent on foreign countries for its oil needs,

but sea transportation, especially with Europe, provides a great advantage over land transportation. While trade is carried out by land due to its border with Turkey, encouraging and making sea transportation to Europe relatively cheaper compared to other alternatives will positively affect Georgia's intra-industry trade.

In the study, the gross domestic product difference, which represents the difference in the size of the market between Georgia and selected European countries and Türkiye, which determines the intra-industry trade, is estimated to be the third important factor determining the intra-industry trade of agriculture and animal husbandry, raw materials, manufactured goods and unclassified goods. Especially in agriculture-animal husbandry and raw material minerals, the insufficiency of domestic demand due to being a small country causes these products to be demanded by countries with relatively larger production and economies, and as the national income difference between Georgia and these countries increases, the intra-industry trade is negatively affected. Therefore, the theoretical sign of the income difference between countries is estimated to be negative, as expected. For Georgia to achieve balance in intra-industry trade in the relevant product groups, it needs to increase its industrial investments for production and accordingly increase product diversity, as we mentioned above.

The per capita national income and openness rate, which are among the determinants of intra-industry trade with Georgia's trade partners, were estimated to be statistically significant only in 3 out of 10 product groups. The fact that the per capita national income, which represents the development and wealth levels of countries, is generally insignificant indicates that Georgia's agricultural and livestock products, which are assumed to have an elasticity of demand less than 1, and the raw material minerals that are the basic inputs of the chemical and industrial sectors, are essential goods and their demand depends on the total national income, which indicates the production potential of the countries, rather than personal income. For European countries and Türkiye, whose industries are quite developed and whose demand power is higher than Georgia's, these products are considered essential goods, and their demand depends on total production. In addition, as in oil-producing countries, a high level of per capita national income does not always mean that the country is developed. It is quite natural for Georgia that the openness rate, which is one of the determinants of intra-industry trade, is significant in the group of beverages and tobacco, processed goods and machinery and equipment products. Georgia has increased the sales of these products, especially to Europe, after 2008, following the mutual free trade agreements. Therefore, we can say that the increase in Georgia's mutual intra-industry trade has been realized with the increase in the country's openness to the outside world. However, for intra-industry trade in other sectors to increase due to openness to the outside world, as mentioned before, Georgia needs to increase its industrial production and product diversity.

The last two determinants of intra-industry trade between Georgia and the countries under study, the per capita income difference and the inter-country mutual

trade imbalance variables, which show the development difference of the countries, are generally statistically insignificant in all commodity groups. As stated in the previous paragraph, since per capita national income is not an effective factor in Georgia's intra-industry trade with the trade partners in question, it is natural that there is no per capita income difference. In addition, a significant portion of the products that Georgia produces and exports are products that concern industrial and total demand rather than personal demand. The per capita income difference and the increase in this difference do not mean that the country is developed under all circumstances, as in the example of oil-producing countries. Finally, the trade differences between countries have not had a significant effect on Georgia's intra-industry trade. We can say that one of the important reasons for this situation is that a country with high energy dependency, for example, must buy this product even if it has a deficit in mutual trade. Georgia is still a country that is dependent on foreign countries for some industrial products, technology and energy due to its production structure. As mentioned before, intra-industry trade may be positively affected, especially when industrial investments are encouraged, as product diversity and income increase. However, if energy needs cannot be met domestically, external dependency will continue.

Conclusion and Recommendation

In this study, to reveal the determinants of intra-industry trade of 10 sub-sectors of SITC Rev4 level (1) goods classification with selected European countries and Türkiye, econometric estimations were made separately for each goods group using the system generalized method of moments. When the analysis results are evaluated, it is shown that as the market size (GDP) of the countries increases, intra-industry trade with Georgia's trade partners in sub-sectors 0, 1, 2, 5, 6, 8 and 9 of SITC goods classification increases, as expected theoretically. As the market size difference between Georgia's trade partners and the countries decreases, intra-industry trade increases in sectors 0, 2, 8 and 9, as expected theoretically. As the trade openness of Georgia with its trade partners increases, intra-industry trade increases in sectors 1, 6 and 7, as expected theoretically. As the physical distance between Georgia's trade partners and the countries increases, intra-industry trade decreases in sectors 2, 3, 5, 8 and 9, as expected theoretically. However, in 6 sectors, the variables of physical distance and trade imbalance between countries gave positive coefficient signs, contrary to the theoretically expected negative signs. In addition, the variable of GDP per capita, which expresses the level of development of countries, gave negative coefficient signs, contrary to the theoretically expected positive signs, in sectors 0, 5 and 7. As the level of development of countries increases, the decrease in intra-industry trade in sectors 0, 5 and 7, and the increase in intra-industry trade with the increase in trade imbalance and physical distance between countries in 6 sectors are out of expectations, but similar results are frequently encountered in the literature.

The results of this econometric analysis show that Georgia's industrial sector is weak, and this situation negatively affects intra-industry trade. In this context,

it is emphasized that the country should focus more on industrialization to strengthen intra-industry trade. In this direction, incentives should be increased especially for the industrial sector and R&D investments to encourage Georgia's industrial production. Directing foreign direct investments in tourism and construction sectors to local production, and investments to be made especially in industrial and technology-based sectors can increase economic diversity and create employment. Georgia needs to increase its product diversity to develop intra-industry trade with its trade partners. It is important to increase the added value of these products by increasing the sales of agricultural, livestock products and raw materials as processed products. Increasing product diversity will reduce Georgia's foreign trade deficit and strengthen its economic resilience. In addition, increasing energy independence and encouraging investments in green energy resources are also important requirements for the sustainability of Georgia's economic growth strategies.

References

1. Grimwade, N. (1989). *International Trade: New Patterns of Trade, Production and Investment*. Oxford University Press on behalf of the Royal Institute of International Affairs, 65(3), 542-553
2. Heckscher, E. & Ohlin, B. (1991). *Heckscher-Ohlin trade theory* (H. Flam & M. J. Flanders, Eds.). MIT Press. (Original work published 1933)
3. Finger, J. M. (1975). Trade overlap and intra-industry trade. *Economic inquiry*, 13(4), 581-589
4. Krugman, P. R. (1981). Intraindustry specialization and the gains from trade. *Journal of political Economy*, 89(5), 959-973.
5. Davis, D. R. (1995). Intra-industry trade: a Heckscher-Ohlin-Ricardo approach. *Journal of international Economics*, 39(3-4), 201-226.
6. Lloyd, P. J., & Lee, H. H. (Eds.). (2002). *Frontiers of research in intra-industry trade* (Vol. 34). Houndmills, Basingstoke, Hampshire, New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
7. Yuan, L. (2012). *Intra-industry trade between Sweden and middle income countries*. Master Thesis, KTH Industrial Engineering and Management.
8. Grubel, H. ve Lloyd, P. J. (1975). *Intra Industry Trade the Theory and Measurement of International Trade in Differentiated Products* (I. Edition). London and Basingstoke: The Macmillan Press Ltd.
9. Greenaway, D., & Milner, C. (1983). On the measurement of intra-industry trade. *The Economic Journal*, 93(372), 900-908.
10. Brühlhart, M. (1994). Marginal intra-industry trade: measurement and relevance for the pattern of industrial adjustment. *Weltwirtschaftliches Archiv*, (H.3), 600-613.
11. Menon, J., & Dixon, P. B. (1997). Intra-industry versus inter-industry trade: Relevance for adjustment costs. *Weltwirtschaftliches Archiv*, (H. 1), 164-169.
12. Azhar, A. K., & Elliott, R. J. (2008). On the measurement of changes in product quality in marginal intra-industry trade. *Review of World Economics*, 144, 225-247.
13. Shelburne, R. C. (1993). Changing trade patterns and the intra-industry trade index: A note. *Weltwirtschaftliches Archiv*, (H. 4), 829-833.
14. Verdoorn P.J. (1960). The intra-bloc trade of benelux. in economic consequences of the size of nations. *Proceedings of a Conference held by the International Economic Association*, 291-329.
15. Michaely, M. (1962). Multilateral balancing in international trade. *The American Economic Review*, 52(4), 685-702.
16. Kojima, K. (1964). The pattern of international trade among advanced countries. *Hitotsubashi Journal of Economics*, 5(1), 16-36.
17. Balassa, B. (1966). Tariff reductions and trade in manufacturers among the industrial countries. *The American Economic Review*, 56(3), 466-473.
18. Aquino, A. (1978). Intra-industry trade and inter-industry specialization as concurrent sources of international trade in manufactures. *Review of World Economics*, 114(2), 275-296.
19. Loertscher, R., & Wolter, F. (1980). Determinants of intra-industry trade: Among countries and across industries. *Review of World Economics*, 116(2), 280-293.
20. Glejser, H., Goossens, K., & Eede, M. V. (1982). Inter-industry versus intra-industry specialization in exports and imports (1959–1970–1973). *Journal of International Economics*, 12(3-4), 363-369.
21. Hamilton, C., & Kniest, P. (1991). Trade liberalisation, structural adjustment and intra-industry trade: a note. *Weltwirtschaftliches Archiv*, 127(2), 356-367.
22. Greenaway, D., Hine, R. C., Milner, C., & Elliott, R. (1994). Adjustment and the measurement of marginal intra-industry trade. *Review of World Economics*, 139 (3), 418-427.
23. Thom, R., & McDowell, M. (1999). Measuring marginal intra-industry trade. *Weltwirtschaftliches Archiv*, 135(1), 48-61.
24. Andresen, M. A. (2010). A cross-industry analysis of intra-industry trade measurement thresholds: Canada and the United States, 1988–1999. *Empirical Economics*, 38, 793-808.
25. Hartman, D. A., Henderson, D. R., & Sheldon, I. M. (1993). A cross-section analysis of intra-industry trade in the US processed food and beverage sectors. *Agricultural and Resource Economics Review*, 22(2), 189-198.
26. Bano, S. (2013). *Horizontal, Vertical and Marginal Intra-Industry International Trade and Their Determinants: Evidence for New Zealand And Australia*. 54 New Zealand Associations of Economists (Nzae) Annual Conference, 3-5 July 2013. Wellington.
27. Falvey, R. E. (1981). Commercial policy and intra-industry trade. *Journal of international economics*, 11(4), 495-511.
28. Sharma, K. (2000). The Pattern and Determinants of Intra-Industry Trade in Australian Manufacturing. *Australian Economic Review*, 33(3), 245-255.
29. Dixit, A. K., & Stiglitz, J. E. (1977). Monopolistic competition and optimum product diversity. *The American economic review*, 67(3), 297-308.

30. Balassa, B. (1979). Intra-industry trade and the integration of developing countries in the world economy. World Bank.
31. Lancaster, K. (1979). Variety, equity, and efficiency: product variety in an industrial society. Columbia University Press. 1979
32. Tharakan, P. M. (1984). Intra-industry trade between the industrial countries and the developing world. *European Economic Review*, 26(1-2), 213-227.
33. Havrylyshyn, O., & Civan, E. (1985). Intra-industry trade among developing countries. *Journal of Development Economics*, 18(2-3), 253-271.
34. Flam, H. & Helpman, E. (1987). Vertical product differentiation and North-South trade. *The American Economic Review*, 77(5), 810-822.
35. Manrique, G. G. (1987). Intra-industry trade between developed and developing countries: The United States and the NICs. *The Journal of Developing Areas*, 481-494.
36. Ballance, R. H., Forstner, H., & Sawyer, W. C. (1992). An empirical examination of the role of vertical product differentiation in North-South trade. *Weltwirtschaftliches Archiv*, 128(2), 330-338.
37. Bhattacharyya, R. (2002). Vertical and horizontal intra industry trade in some Asian and Latin American less developed countries. *Journal of Economic Integration*, 17(2), 273-296.
38. Thorpe, M., & Zhang, Z. (2005). Study of the measurement and determinants of intra-industry trade in East Asia. *Asian Economic Journal*, 19(2), 231-247.
39. Zhang, Y., & Clark, D. P. (2009). Pattern and determinants of United States' intra-industry trade. *The International Trade Journal*, 23(3), 325-356.
40. Sunde, T., Chidoko, C., & Zivanomoyo, J. (2009). Determinants of Intra Industry Trade between Zimbabwe and its Trading Partners in the Southern African Development Community (1990-2006). *Journal of Social Sciences* 5(1), 16-21.
41. Thorpe, M., & Zhang, Z. (2005). Study of the measurement and determinants of intra-industry trade in East Asia. *Asian Economic Journal*, 19(2), 231-247.
42. Sawyer, W. C., Sprinkle, R. L., & Tochkov, K. (2010). Patterns and determinants of intra-industry trade in Asia. *Journal of Asian Economics*, 21(5), 485-493.
43. Mulenga, M. C. (2012). Determinants of intra-industry trade between Zambia and its trading partners in the Southern African Development Community (SADC). *Ethiopian Journal of Economics*, 21(1), 107-132.
44. Yuan, L. (2012). Intra-industry trade between Sweden and middle income countries. Master Thesis, KTH Industrial Engineering and Management.
45. Sotomayor, M. (2012). Patterns and determinants of intra industry trade for the Mexican non-maquiladora manufacturing Industry. *The Journal of Business Inquiry*, 11(1), 33-57.
46. Saray, M. (2013). Türkiye'nin endüstri içi ticaretinin belirleyicileri: temel dış ticaret partnerleri ile panel veri analizi. Ph.D. Thesis.
47. Łapinska, J. (2014). Determinants of intra-industry trade in agricultural and food products between Poland and EU countries. *Danube*, 5(3), 159-172.
48. Trupkiewicz, M. (2015). Determinants of the horizontal and vertical intra-industry trade between Norway and the European Union. Master's thesis.
49. Nisa, F. C. (2017). Patterns and determinants of intra-industry trade between indonesia and trading partner countries. *Journal of Developing Economies*, 2(1), 27-37.
50. Justyna, L, Grzegorz, K & Radoslaw, D. (2019). Country-specific determinants of intra-industry trade in clothing and footwear between poland and european union countries. *BazTech*, 27(4), 1-6.
51. Vidya, C. T., & Prabheesh, K. P. (2019). Intra-industry trade between India and Indonesia. *Bulletin of Monetary Economics and Banking*, 21, 511-530.
52. Nguyen, H. M., Quan, B. Q. M., LE Huong, V., & Tran, T. V. (2020). Determinants of intra-industry trade between vietnam and countries in tpp. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(1), 123-129.
53. Özer, Ö. (2021). Türkiye otomotiv sektöründe endüstri içi ticareti etkileyen faktörler üzerine ekonometrik bir analiz. Master's thesis.
54. González, C. V., Muñoz, C. A. P., Bolaños, J. F., & Aguilera-Prado, M. (2022). Regional determinants of Colombian intra-industry trade. *International Journal of Trade and Global Markets*, 15(4), 391-405.
55. Ekayanti, D. F., & Setiawina, N. D. (2023). Determinants of Indonesia's Intra-Industry Trade of Cosmetic Commodity (HS Code 3304) with Trade Partners Of APEC-4 Countries. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 8(1), 77-85.
56. Aggarwal, S. (2023). The empirical measurement and determinants of intra-industry trade for a developing country. *Journal of Applied Economic Sciences (JAES)*, 18(81), 182-220.
57. Hayakawa, K. (2005). Small sample bias properties of the system GMM estimator in dynamic panel data models. *Economics letters*, 95(1), 32-38.
58. Anderson, T. W., & Hsiao, C. (1981). Estimation of dynamic models with error components. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 76(375), 598-606
59. Anderson, T. W., & Hsiao, C. (1982). Formulation and estimation of dynamic models using panel data. *Journal of Econometrics*, 18(1), 47-82.
60. Hansen, L. P., & Singleton, K. J. (1982). Generalized instrumental variables estimation of nonlinear rational expectations models. *Econometrica: Journal of the Econometric Society*, 50(5), 1269-1286.
61. Arellano, M., & Bond, S. (1991). Some tests of specification for panel data: Monte Carlo evidence and an application to employment equations. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 58(2), 277-297.
62. Arellano, M., & Bover, O. (1995). Another look at the instrumental variable estimation of error-components models. *Journal of Econometrics*, 68(1), 29-51
63. Blundell, R., & Bond, S. (1998). Initial conditions and moment restrictions in dynamic panel data models. *Journal of econometrics*, 87(1), 115-143.
64. Hansen, L. P. (2007). Generalized method of moments estimation. *Macroeconomics and time series analysis*, 20(4), 1-14.